

Improvement of Humanity in War: Perspectives from Recent Progressions in Social Law Sciences

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Abstract

It is critical to protect the humanity of people during war. Recently, it has been achieved significant progressions in social law sciences, including both the theory of armed police and party disciplines against democratic crimes, by which it is perspective to improve the humanity for people during war. For the theory of armed police, it was Zi-Jian Cai who started and led the democratic law execution in China, supporting the theory of armed police. It is more associative for the armed police to the court, while the court can punish the officers/soldiers making crimes against people in war, such as the Japanese officers/soldiers killing Chinese people in World War II. Thus, it is perspective for the court to educate and restrict the armed police to protect the humanity of people in war. For the party disciplines against democratic crimes, it is the war that makes the country devote most social resources to battlefields, while neglect the welfare, as evidenced in Russia-Ukraine War. It is the discipline of communist parties to support humanity and improve poverty of people including the need of women, children and refugees in war, as evidenced in Europe and China during wartime. It was the movement of “Marx-MingXun calling for competitive election” during 2010-2014 that improved the democratic image of communist parties, made it practice the discipline for humanity and poverty, and revived the communist parties synchronously worldwide. Thus, it is perspective for the communist parties to improve humanity of people in war without causing autocracy.

Keywords: *Humanity, Democratic Law Execution, Armed Police, Communist Party, Marx-MingXun Calling for Competitive Election.*

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Introduction

Recently till now, it has been occurring two wars attracting the attention of the whole world, the Russia-Ukraine War (Cui & Xing, 2022; Goldstein & Waechter, 2023) and Gaza Conflict(Niu, 2023). Because it is the character of war to damage and kill the opponent, it is inevitable that the war would result in some hurt and death of innocent people. Accordingly, it is imperative to consider how to improve the humanity of people during war. In this article, it is highlighted this issue by perspective application of recent progressions in social law sciences.

Related Theories

The Theory of Armed Police

Democracy calling for law execution in China

Since the establishment of United States of America(USA) as the first kingless country, there occurred the continual revolution during the recent hundreds of years in many countries to achieve the new

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republic system. For the royal system, in confrontation of such revolutionary and violent actions as war, murder, terror, and so on, the royal family are not able to pay much sacrifice, while the republic system does not have such defect, thereby has achieved many revolutionary victories(Cai, 2017, 2018a). At present time, China, Brazil, Russia and so on have all overthrown the rule of king and realized the republic system.

However, some republic countries instead adopted the autocratic system by party or religion for a period of time in history, such as the Republic of China, the Soviet Union, and so on, with the ruling party unafraid of the threats of death, and thus stronger than the royal family. In China, the support from army for autocracy of party has been lasting for decades of years, manifesting as the military suppression of people on TianAnMen Square, which was known as the pessimistic June 4th Incident of China in 1989. To realize the democracy of republics, it is necessary to overcome the new and stronger autocracy from party and army.

From the end of 1999 to the beginning of 2000, with the technological assistance as the satellite thermoacoustic sound and satellite television network, Zi-Jian Cai began promoting the democracy in China(Cai, 2017, 2018a). Soon, on the street of HongQiao District of Shanghai, Cai realized that the country was supplied by such developed areas as Shanghai and so on, and thus should be the property of paid taxes from these areas(Cai, 2017, 2018a). Cai immediately recalled and cited the term “Property of paid taxes” previously learned from television(Cai, 2017, 2018a), and admired this American concept of country really wise and correct. By directing the satellites to shout in Chinese loudly and repeatedly in Shanghai, Suzhou and on the train, Cai gradually influenced the Chinese people in television and broke through the unhealthy situation in China after the June 4th Incident in 1989 that most people in China did not dare to say democracy(Cai, 2018a).

However, the leaders of China ZeMin Jiang and Peng Li at that time neglected this advocacy of democracy. In response, around 2001 Cai and the Chinese people said that it would be legal to call for police to promote the democracy by force, while the people could even actively execute against autocracy violently by law. This was the worldwide famous movement in television as “Democracy calling for law execution in China” or “Democratic law execution in China”, eliciting high attention from the world people(Cai, 2017, 2018a).

Some provincial and municipal leaders in China paid attention to this law for democracy during that time. Before 2005, the municipal leaders KuangDi Xu and LiangYu Chen in Shanghai recognized the law of democracy in television(Cai, 2017, 2018b). From 2008 to 2014, in television the Muslims in XinJiang, HuaHua Huang and Yang Wang as the highest leaders in GuangDong, the masses, cadres and leaders in the old liberated areas of New Fourth Army in Northern JiangSu all concerned about the democracy as the law of republic country(Cai, 2017, 2018b). In television, the art performances of China Central Television such as “The Same Song” and “Happy Travel in China” were the happy gatherings of artists and audiences to discuss democracy(Cai, 2017, 2018b).

Before then, for achieving the victory of democracy either by nonviolent march and strike, or by violent revolution and coup, the law had usually been utilized by the autocrats for order. It was not the juristic concept the country belonging to people that was novel, which had been common for socialism for a long time, but the people had not utilized it to promote democracy. For Cai to start and lead the democratic law execution in China this time, it was the first time for the law force to help the people strive for democracy, becoming one of the historical turning points for the democratic forces to achieve significant dominance.

The theory of armed police

Prior to 2000, Zi-Jian Cai had already utilized the internationalization and world police to protect the legal people in Shanghai. In 2001 Cai pointed out that the police could act and shoot earlier once the opponent initiated any illegal action, and could even monitor the generals and officers of army from time to time, making them compliant(Cai, 2017, 2018a).

Inspired by controlling the strong army, Cai, the satellite operators, the Chinese and world people imitated to equip the armed police with heavy weapons to war against the army, including the missiles, the rocket artilleries, the helicopters, and so on. A portion of military budget could be covered by police, improving the efficiency of using budgets and making the armed police stronger than the present army(Cai, 2016, 2017, 2018a).

Later, Cai wrote a theoretical book “Weapons, Armed Troops and War - The Armed Police Winning over the Army”, with the English version of which published in Germany(ISBN : 978-3-659-95272-2)(Cai, 2016, 2017, 2018a).

It is necessary to point out that Mauritius and Costa Rica have already made more armed police than army in their countries, but they still needed to support the theory of armed police(Cai, 2016, 2017, 2018a). The new practice of democratic law execution exactly supported the theory of armed police, preventing the provincial and municipal armed police from professional autocracy when they becoming too strong and too many(Cai, 2017, 2018a). This was the social basis for the theory of armed police stronger than army but still protecting the democracy, as the provincial and municipal police leaders staying in the same cities with the law people(Cai, 2017, 2018a).

The Disciplines of Specialized Parties against Democratic Crimes

The movement of “Marx-MingXun calling for competitive election”

In 2010, to rectify the autocratic Communist Party of China, based on the previous experience of Zi-Jian Cai’s father MingXun Cai as one of the earliest Communists to run for competitive election for plant manager in China, Zi-Jian Cai started the movement of “Marx-MingXun calling for competitive election”(Cai, 2017, 2018c), educating the communists necessary to understand and compare the competitive candidates for the objectivity of democracy, while criticizing the electoral fraud of communists in China, Soviet Union, and so on.

The struggle against democratic crimes with the disciplines of specialized parties

For the democratic country, if most people make illegal choices, then the democratic decision would be illegal and criminal, which threatens the legality of democratic system. On January 15, 2012, Zi-Jian Cai and the sportsmen on television in China recognized that, with the rectification of “Marx-MingXun calling for competitive election”, the communist parties in various countries acquired the ability of applying their own party disciplines to be away from or even struggle against the democratic crimes in congresses at various levels(Cai, 2017, 2018c). Similarly, other specialized parties, such as the various justice parties in the world, the Democratic Progressive Party in Taiwan, the Democratic National Construction Association of China, and so on, did not need to make the rectification and were directly able to apply the specialized disciplines of their own party to be away from or even struggle against the democratic crimes in congresses at various levels(Cai, 2017, 2018c).

The struggle against democratic crimes with party discipline is different from the traditional arguments from opposite parties against government, with the sharp arguments not necessarily legal but just to attract voters. The struggle against democratic crimes with party discipline depends on the legal disciplines of specialized parties, which may not necessarily be welcome by many aggressive illegal voters.

The revival of communist parties in world by “Marx-MingXun calling for competitive election”

“Marx-MingXun calling for competitive election” during that time increased the democratic image of various communist parties worldwide away from the big influence of the autocratic Communist Party of China. Then, for the first time in history, the communist parties worldwide in turn participated the practice of struggle against democratic crimes with party discipline supporting humanity and improving poverty, so that “Marx-MingXun calling for competitive election” synchronously revived the communist parties in various countries in the whole world, especially those in East Europe, Brazil, and so on, becoming the historical manifestations in television(Cai, 2017, 2018c).

On December 3, 2014, because of the significant international and historical effects of “Marx-MingXun calling for competitive election”, the Chinese and foreign people in television suggested to segregate this history away from other political influences. In this regard, Zi-Jian Cai declared the movement “Marx-MingXun calling for competitive election” ended successfully(Cai, 2017, 2018c).

Court to Improve Humanity of People in War

Crimes of Army to People Sometimes in War

Sometimes, the criminal actions from army in war are very detrimental, killing many people without any control or limit. The famous "Nanjing Massacre" made by the Japanese army of invasion killed about 300000 people in Nanjing(Li, 2005; Zhang, 2007). Even in today, in the Gaza Conflict, it is worldwide known that the Israeli army have repeatedly violated the international humanitarian law, especially against civilians(Mahwati & Nanda, 2022).

In summary, the army may sometimes make crimes against civilian people during war.

Court Penalty to Crimes of Army on People in War

The court of law takes action to sentence and punish the evidenced army crimes against the people. For the famous "Nanjing Massacre" made by the Japanese army killing many Chinese people, the Tokyo War Crimes Trial sentenced and punished the top related Japanese generals(Cheng, 2008), while the Nanjing War Crimes Tribunal targeted other officials(Jing, 2013). In today, the world is angry at the violence of Israeli army to Palestinian civilians(Mahwati & Nanda, 2022). In consistence, the International Criminal Court(ICC) in Europe accused that Israel committed war crimes and crimes against humanity in Gaza Conflict(Soraya et al., 2024), while South Africa sued the International Court of Justice against Israel to be the genocide to Palestinian(Akbar & Genovés, 2024), both of which were severe to the leaders and generals of Israel if arrested outside Israel in future.

In summary, the court of law takes the duty to sentence and punish the evidenced crimes made by army against the civilian people during war.

Court More Associative to Educate and Restrict Armed Police in War

The theory of armed police is advantageous in that the democratic law execution can prevent the provincial and municipal armed police from professional autocracy when they becoming too strong and too many as the police leaders staying in the same cities as the law people(Cai, 2017, 2018a).

Besides, herein there is another advantage for the armed police, which can reduce the crimes against civilian people during war. Because, as demonstrated above, the court of law takes the duty to sentence and punish the crimes made against the people during war, the police more associative to the court would receive more education and restriction from court against crimes on people in war. This would reduce both intention and courage of armed police to make crimes against people in war.

In summary, the court would educate and restrict the more associative armed police against making crimes to people during war.

Discipline of Communist Parties for Humanity in War

War to Reduce Welfare Fund

In war, the social resources are devoted mostly to the frontlines, which reduces the budget for humanity. In the present Russian-Ukrainian War, it has been analyzed that the National Welfare Fund has shrunk by almost a third and continues to shrink in Russia(Sliusarenko et al., 2024). Reduction of welfare fund is a severe consequence of war that every country must face.

Communist Discipline to Support Humanity

As mentioned above, “Marx-MingXun calling for competitive election” improved the democratic image of various communist parties worldwide, made the communist parties in turn participate the practice of struggle against democratic crimes with party discipline supporting humanity and improving poverty, and synchronously revived the communist parties in various countries in the whole world(Cai, 2017, 2018c).

Accordingly, it is now safe to apply the discipline of communist parties to support humanity and improve poverty, unnecessary to worry about the old autocratic influences of communist parties.

Communists Evidenced to Help Women and Children in War

The women and children are weak and negatively affected by war. It is necessary to consider special help to them during war. Communist parties in various countries consider such issue of humanity. There are many examples, with some of which as evidenced in the followings:

During the Greek Civil War, the Communist Party of Greece evacuated 28,000 children from villages in northern Greece in 1948(Danforth, 2003), obviously for the purpose of improving the safety of children in war.

During the time of Anti-Japanese War in China in 20th Century, in the areas controlled by the Communist Party of China, both women and children were well cared(Wen & Luo, 2010). Especially, there was a slogan as “Long Live the Children” in the communist Yan'an period in China(Yu & Wang, 2021).

In summary, it is well evidenced that the communist parties have been disciplined to help women and children during wartime.

Communists Evidenced to Help Refugees in War

The refugees caused by war are extra burden to the welfare system, and require extra help. Communist parties in various countries are also devoted to such issue of humanity. There are also many examples, as the followings:

Due to the Greco-Turkish War, more than one million Anatolian Greek refugees influenced the traditional balance of mass politics at the electoral level, and contributed to the electoral gains of the Greek Communist Party(KKE)(Poulos, 2022). During that time in Europe, the communist parties in Europe manifested and operated as autocratic in tendency, negative influencing the society as a whole(Poulos, 2022). From now on, with “Marx-MingXun calling for competitive election” improving the democratic image of various communist parties worldwide(Cai, 2017, 2018c), it would no longer be present such negative social effect.

During the time of Anti-Japanese War in China in 20th Century, in the areas controlled by the Communist Party of China, it was successful in rescuing and arranging a lot of refugees, especially many refugees going there from other places of the country(Chang & Guan, 2011; Ma, 2004).

In summary, it is evidenced that the communist parties have been disciplined to rescue and arrange refugees during wartime.

Conclusions

It is important to protect the humanity and improve the poverty of people during wartime. In this article, it is supplemented new perspectives on this issue from the recent progressions in social law sciences, mainly as (i) the theory of armed police and (ii) the party discipline of communists against democratic crimes neglecting humanity and poverty in war.

For the theory of armed police, it was Zi-Jian Cai who started and led the democratic law execution in China, which supported the theory of armed police. It is well evidenced that the court can punish the officers/soldiers making crimes against people in war, such as the Japanese officers/soldiers killing Chinese people in World War II. On the other hand, it is more associative for the armed police to the

court, so that it is perspective for the court to educate and restrict the armed police to protect the humanity of people in war.

For the party discipline against democratic crimes neglecting humanity and poverty in war, it is the nature of war that makes the country devote most of social resources to battlefields, as evidenced by the shrink of National Welfare Fund in Russia during the present Russian-Ukrainian War. It is the discipline of communist parties to support humanity and improve poverty of people including the need of women, children and refugees in war, as demonstrated by cases in both Europe and China during wartime. It was the movement of “Marx-MingXun calling for competitive election” during 2010-2014 that improved the democratic image of communist parties, made it practice to struggle with the discipline for humanity and poverty, so that revived the communist parties synchronously worldwide. Thus, now it is perspective for the communist parties to improve the humanity of people in war without anxiety for causing autocracy.

In Table 1, it is outlined the two new perspectives to improve humanity in war from recent progressions in social law sciences.

Table 1 Two New Perspectives to Improve Humanity in War

Theory of Armed Police	Communist Discipline for Humanity
Due to the court responsible for sentencing and punishing the officers/soldiers making crimes to people in war, the court more associative with armed police to educate and restrict the armed police to protect the humanity of people in war.	Discipline of communist parties to support humanity and improve poverty of people including the need of women, children and refugees in war, with the movement of “Marx-MingXun calling for competitive election” improving the democratic image of communist parties and reducing the anxiety of autocracy.

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Author's Contributions

The sole one author responsible for all of this article.

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